

A recurrence formula for prime numbers using the Smarandache or Totient functions

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Abstract

In this paper we report a recurrence formula to obtain the n-th prime in terms of (n-1)th prime and as a function of Smarandache or Totient function.

In [1] the Smarandache Prime Function is defined as follows:

$$P: N \rightarrow (0,1)$$

$$\text{where: } P(n) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } n \text{ is prime} \\ 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is composite} \end{cases}$$

This function can be used to determine the number of primes $\pi(N)$ less or equal to some integer N and to determine a recurrence formula to obtain the n-th prime starting from the (n-1)th one.

In fact:

$$\pi(N) = \sum_{i=1}^N (1 - P(i))$$

and

$$p_{n+1} = 1 + p_n + \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i)$$

where p_n is the n-th prime.

The first equation is obvious because $(1 - P(i))$ is equal to 1 every time i is a prime. Let's prove the second one.

Since $p_{n+1} < 2p_n$ [2] where p_{n+1} and p_n are the $(n+1)$ th and n -th prime respectively, the following equality holds [3]:

$$\sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i) = \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{p_{n+1}-1} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i) + \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i) = \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{p_{n+1}-1} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i)$$

because $\sum_{j=p_{n+1}}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i) = 0$ being $P(p_{n+1}) = 0$ by definition.

As:

$$\sum_{j=p_n+1}^{p_{n+1}-1} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i) = \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{p_{n+1}-1} 1 = (p_{n+1} - 1) - (p_n + 1) + 1 = p_{n+1} - p_n - 1$$

we get:

$$p_{n+1} = 1 + p_n + \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j P(i) \quad \text{q.e.d}$$

According to this result we can obtain p_{n+1} once we know p_n and $P(i)$.

We report now two expressions for $P(i)$ using the Smarandache function $S(n)$ [4] and the well known Totient function $\varphi(n)$ [5].

- $P(i) = 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{S(i)}{i} \right\rfloor$ for $i > 4$
- $P(i) = 1 - \left\lfloor \frac{\varphi(i)}{i-1} \right\rfloor$ for $i > 1$

where $\lfloor n \rfloor$ is the floor function [6]. Let's prove now the first equality.

By definition of Smarandache function $S(i) = i$ for $i \in P \cup \{1, 4\}$ where P is the set of prime numbers [6]. Then $\left\lfloor \frac{S(i)}{i} \right\rfloor$ is equal to 1 if i is a prime number and equal to zero for all composite > 4 being $S(i) \leq i$ [4].

About the second equality we can notice that by definition $\varphi(n) < n$ for $n > 1$ and $\varphi(n) = n-1$ if and only if n is a prime number [5]. So $\varphi(n) \leq n-1$ for $n > 1$ and this implies that $\left\lfloor \frac{\varphi(i)}{i-1} \right\rfloor$ is equal to 1 if i is a prime number and equal to zero otherwise..

Then:

$$p_{n+1} = 1 + p_n + \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j \left(1 - \left\lfloor \frac{S(i)}{i} \right\rfloor \right) \quad \text{for } n > 2$$

and

$$p_{n+1} = 1 + p_n + \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j \left(1 - \left\lfloor \frac{\varphi(i)}{i-1} \right\rfloor \right) \quad \text{for } n \geq 1$$

According to the result obtained in [7] for the Smarandache function:

$$S(i) = i + 1 - \left[\sum_{k=1}^i i^{-\left(i \cdot \sin\left(k! \frac{\pi}{i}\right)\right)^2} \right]$$

and in [3] for the following function:

$$\left[\frac{i}{k} \right] - \left[\frac{i-1}{k} \right] = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k \text{ divide } i \\ 0 & \text{if } k \text{ doesn't divide } i \end{cases}$$

the previous recurrence formulas can be further simplified as follows:

$$p_{n+1} = 1 + p_n + \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j \left(1 - \frac{\left(i + 1 - \left[\sum_{k=1}^i i^{-\left(i \cdot \sin\left(k! \frac{\pi}{i}\right)\right)^2} \right] \right)}{i} \right) \quad \text{for } n > 2$$

and

$$p_{n+1} = 1 + p_n + \sum_{j=p_n+1}^{2p_n} \prod_{i=p_n+1}^j \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^i \left(1 - \left(\left[\frac{i}{k} \right] - \left[\frac{i-1}{k} \right] \right) \right)}{i-1} \right) \quad \text{for } n \geq 1$$

References.

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